

LUDWIG-MAXIMILIANS-UNIVERSITÄT MÜNCHEN
GESCHWISTER-SCHOLL-INSTITUT FÜR POLITIKWISSENSCHAFT

The Specters of Populism

A Hegelian Approach to the Failure of Constitutional Sublation in
Populist Phenomenology

Borna A. Barzinmehr

Term Paper

In Debates in Democracy Research

Course Instructors: Dr. Petra Stykow, Dr. Stefan Matern

Submission Date: 09.03.25

Table of Contents

Exordium.....	2
Hegelian dialectics.....	4
Servant of the People.....	6
Constitutional Sublation.....	8
Populistic Pseudosublation.....	11
Conclusion.....	13
Bibliography.....	14

Exordium

There is no novelty in invoking the *Spectre* of Engels and Marx in a reference to Populism. Yet, the inexorable perennality of its core characteristics—as the presence of something neither fully absent nor entirely present, something that lingers, haunts, and inscribes itself upon the present without yielding to complete apprehension—renders Populism the truer spectre. Through ever-shifting antagonisms, it transcends the temporal materialisation to reconstitute itself in different epochs within disparate ideological configurations. The essence of Populism is not that of a latent telos awaiting realisation; instead of unfolding toward a singular historical fulfillment, Populism oscillates as a pervasive rupture of the political currents.

The constant self-reconstitution of Populism that permeates in the failure of finding a closure, provoked my curiosity to approach its phenomenology through the Hegelian epistemic framework. The constant negation of the political order—whether the Populist is in opposition or in government—reflects two Hegelian principles: Negation and Sublation. The first, negation, is the lifeblood of Populism, manifesting as an antagonistic force that defines itself in opposition to an established order—whether decrying elite domination from the periphery or dismantling institutional constraints from within. Yet, negation alone does not capture the full movement of Populism, for its persistence lies in its ability to reconstitute itself perpetually. This leads to the second principle: sublation (*Aufhebung*), the process by which contradiction is not abolished but rather preserved, reconfigured, and elevated into a new formal institution.

Populist dialectics never fully eradicates the structures they seek to overturn.¹ It absorbs and reconfigures them, producing new iterations of political antagonism that sustain its presence. In this way, Populism does not establish an enduring alternative to the order it negates but rather inscribes itself as an indeterminate force—neither wholly exterior to the system nor entirely subsumed within it. Its existence, then, is neither one of Hegelian historical resolution nor of ideological culmination, but of continuous return, a phenomenon that remains unfulfilled precisely because it thrives on the very impossibility of closure. This paradox, wherein negation becomes the means of persistence, is what situates the *spectrality* of the Populist phenomenon within the logic of Hegelian dialectics.

The Populist *spectre* was first invoked by Ionescu and Gellner (1969) as the spectre that is “haunting the world,”² and again as “the spectre [that] continues to pursue the sceptre”³ in the

¹ Jan-Werner Müller, *What Is Populism?* (2017), p. 57

² Ghița. Ionescu and Ernest Gellner, *Populism; Its Meaning and National Characteristics*. (1969)

³ Daniele Albertazzi and Duncan McDonnell, *Twenty-First Century Populism: The Spectre of Western European Democracy* (2008).

name of the people⁴ by Albertazzi and McDonnell (2008). While decades apart, the assessments of Populism remain contemporarily relevant. My adaptation of specterality in the construction of this work is centered on the Hegelian dialectics between Servant and Master, and a divorce from the normative conventions of spectre as a political *Zeitgeist*. The idea of Populism as a *Zeitgeist* was explicitly addressed by Mudde (2004), who argued that Populism had become an overarching ideological current influencing mainstream political parties and institutions.⁵ The idea of an all-encompassing Populist *Zeitgeist* was rejected by Rooduijn⁶ who posited that Populism should be understood as just a periodical political mood rather than a permanent ideological shift.⁷ Following Rooduijn, I invoke the spectre as a manifestation of a *spectrum*, wherein Populism unfolds in a rejection of the binary demarcation of the Servant and Master in Hegelian dialectics. The spectrality of the Populist phenomenon, consequently, neither fits within the self-consciousness of the Servant nor the Master. It exists in a liminal state, oscillating between servitude and sovereignty, being and becoming, yet never fully resolving into one or the other.

A shared observation among many scholars is that Populism is fundamentally hostile to the mechanisms and values associated with Constitutional Democracy.⁸⁹¹⁰¹¹ It emerges from the belief that the system, rather than serving the people, has been captured by immoral elites –the Hegelian masters– who deny the true people their recognition. When populists succeed in taking power, they do not resolve this antagonism. Instead, they reconfigure it to maintain the antagonism of constitutionalist principles.¹² Observing the failure of populists to reconcile with power in constitutional democracies, the following research question is posed: *How does the Hegelian dialectic explain the Populist's liminality between opposition and incumbency?*

Approaching this question through abductive logic and critical realism, I explored authoritative sources on Populism and Hegelian logic, to propose the following thesis: The Populist's liminality from opposition to incumbency reveals a state of spectrality in which Populism neither fully integrates into the constitutional framework nor fully transcends it. Instead, persists in a cycle of antagonistic negation, wherein –through the perpetual construction of crises– it maintains an artificial oppositionality to the imagined enemies of the people.

⁴ Ibid.

⁵ Cas Mudde, “The Populist *Zeitgeist*,” *Government and Opposition*, no. 4 (2004): 541–63

⁶ Matthijs Rooduijn, “A Populist *Zeitgeist*? The Impact of Populism on Parties, Media and the Public in Western Europe,” Thesis, (2013)

⁷ Mudde et al., “Populism: An Ideational Approach,” essay, in *The Oxford Handbook of Populism* (2019) 45–71.

⁸ Kurt Weyland et al., “Populism: A Political-Strategic Approach,” essay, in *The Oxford Handbook of Populism* (2019), 71–103

⁹ Kirk A. Hawkins et al., “Populism and Its Causes,” essay, in *The Oxford Handbook of Populism* (2019), 340–65.

¹⁰ Duncan Kelly et al., “Populism and the History of Popular Sovereignty,” essay, in *The Oxford Handbook of Populism* (2019). 642–72

¹¹ Müller et al., “Populism and Constitutionalism,” essay, in *The Oxford Handbook of Populism* (2019), 743–65.

¹² Ibid.

Hegelian dialectics

Hegel contends that self-consciousness begins with a simple “I” as a solitary awareness of oneself. This initial awareness is yet incomplete, as it is not enough for the “I” to merely exist in isolation.¹³ The self-conscious mind soon learns that it cannot be fully realised or defined by its own existence alone. It needs an “Other” to recognise and affirm its being. This realisation marks a crucial moment in the development of self-consciousness by dividing it into two forms: One that is self-sufficient, existing purely for its own will and desires, and the *other* that is dependent, defined in relation to something outside of itself. Hegel identifies the first as the *master*, and the latter as the *servant*.¹⁴

This process of self-consciousness is deeply tied to the suppression or conquering of the “Other.”¹⁵ In the early stages, each consciousness is a subjective abstraction, perceiving itself as the measure of all things. This subjective self-consciousness is driven by the *desire* (*Begierde*) to collide with an external object in order to achieve objectivity. This interaction leads to the development of a more concrete form of self-consciousness, which Hegel describes as *Becoming*—a concept that reflects being while reconciling the notions of reality as both changeable and unchanging.¹⁶

For Hegel, *negation* is an essential component of *desire*.¹⁷ To define being, one must also define not-being.¹⁸ In isolation, being is incomplete; it requires negation in order to progress into the next moment of becoming. This creates a cyclical process of being and becoming, which is perpetuated through *negation* and *sublation*, where each stage negates and preserves elements of what came before, elevating them to a higher synthesis.¹⁹

Hegel applies his method of reaching Self-consciousness through the negation of external forces at the individual-person level. I expound the relevance of this to Populism through applying Self-consciousness at a macrocosmic level to the collective. The master-servant dialectic dramatises this emergence: one comes to know oneself by encountering and recognising the *self* in others. This first encounter, however, is a unilateral negation. Hegel suggests that it is a matter of survival, that one group relents its selfhood to subjugation to retain its unilateral

¹³ Georg Wilhelm Friedrich Hegel, A. V. Miller, and J. N. Findlay, *Phenomenology of Spirit* by G.W.F. Hegel. Transl. by A.V. Miller with Analysis of the Text and Foreword by J.N. Findlay (1977). 118–119

¹⁴ *Ibid.*

¹⁵ David Aristotelis Fusiek, “Hegel in a Postcolonial World: Populist Authoritarianism, Postcolonialism, and the Master–Slave Dialectic,” 4–30

¹⁶ *Ibid.* 18

¹⁷ Hegel, 60

¹⁸ *Ibid.*, 81

¹⁹ *Ibid.*,

self-consciousness.²⁰ They surrender their claim for recognition. The other, by contrast, asserts their self-assertion and is recognised as the sovereign party. This uneven relationship marks the second stage of the dialectic, where the sovereign master transcends immediate materiality, and the servant assumes a subordinate role due to their inability to achieve the same level of self-consciousness.

Initially, the master achieves a sense of independence and power through dominance, while the servant becomes the means through which the master's negations are fulfilled. Then, the master's consciousness becomes passive, relying on the labor and subordination of the servant, while, through labor, the servant is able to negate the external world, leading to a sense of self-awareness and independence.²¹

As the servant gains consciousness of its role in history, the master's consciousness becomes dependent on the servant. This reciprocal relationship signals the emergence of mutual recognition, which is the ultimate goal of the dialectic. Hegel views this dialectical movement as the beginning of history, where the resolution of the dialectic is symbolised by the formation of a state.²² In Hegel's account, when self-consciousness encounters the Other, it is confronted with the loss of its singular self. Each consciousness, in confrontation with the Other, seeks to monopolise and sublate the Other, viewing it as an "unessential, negatively characterised object,"²³ crucial to overcoming the immediacy.

²⁰ Fusiek, 7

²¹ Ibid, 9

²² Ibid, 20

²³ Robert Sinnerbrink, "Recognitive Freedom: Hegel and the Problem of Recognition," 2004, 271–95

Servant of the People

The Populist consciousness is distinctly Manichean. Whereas they are the representative of the *authentic* and morally pure people, the elite masters are decadent and morally corrupt.²⁴ The Populist servant speaks for *all people*, with people being an anecdote to the inherently exclusionary political force of the Populist. The individuals who do not align with the Populist consciousness are as externalised as the *others*, the elites.²⁵ The claim of the Populist to represent the interest of the people does not need any empirical evidence, as its foundation is on a moral judgment of who is truly part of the people.²⁶

This political behaviour does not differ in democratic contexts.²⁷ Paradoxically, while the Populist may appear to advocate for democratic representation, it relies on a symbolic representation of the people, outside the formal mechanisms of democracy. The people, as Populists envision them, are a fictional, morally homogeneous entity, whose will exists in opposition to the outcomes of actual elections and democratic processes. Their will is embodied in the voice of the Populist.²⁸

Müller recognises this as a pattern of political distortion and denial of social realities.²⁹ An apt example she makes is the claim to the “Silent majority” used by both Nixon and Trump during their elections.³⁰ The people cannot be fully known or represented in a static form, and the notion that a single political entity can encapsulate the will of the people disregards the fluid nature of citizenship.

This lack of social awareness of the Populist can be explained through how the servant’s self-awareness is shaped entirely by its opposition to the master—its identity is reactive rather than autonomous. Similarly, Populists construct their legitimacy through opposition to an imagined exploitative elite and alignment to an imagined people. By denying the contested identity of *the people*, the Populist, like the servant, remains trapped in a cycle of negation, defining themselves only in contrast to an external enemy rather than through substantive self-realisation in a constitutional democracy.

This becomes an architecture for continued antagonism and dialectical oppositionality to the general system that remains unchanging and sovereign as new elites are elected to the office. This

²⁴ Müller, *What Is Populism?* (2017). 25

²⁵ *Ibid.*

²⁶ *Ibid.* 28

²⁷ *Ibid.*

²⁸ *Ibid.* 35

²⁹ *Ibid.*

³⁰ *Ibid.* 27

system is the framework of governance constituted by the constitution. The Populist antagonises the constitution and its formal institutions that do not conform to its vision, as is evident in its rejection of established democratic mechanisms.³¹ It is, however, a misapprehension to view populists as anti-institutional actors, as they do not reject institutions wholesale. Rather, they reject institutions that fail to produce what they deem to be the morally correct political outcomes.³² This distinction is crucial: while in opposition, populists cast institutions as obstructions to the popular will, yet, once in power, they eagerly appropriate and repurpose those same institutions to entrench their own authority.³³

In parallel, contrary to conventional wisdom, Populism also does not necessarily reject constitutionalism. Müller contends that populists engage in a form of *Populist constitutionalism*, one that subverts rather than safeguards democratic pluralism.³⁴ Unlike traditional constitutional framers who seek to establish a system of governance that mediates between competing political forces, the Populist instrumentalises constitutions to consolidate their vision of a singular, morally pure people and to entrench their own authority.³⁵ Similarly, Paulina Ochoa Espejo argues that the way Populism is conceived depends largely on how we conceptualise "the people" (the demos) in a democracy.³⁶ Jason Frank shifts the analytical focus from the question of who constitutes the people to how the people act – rearing towards Populism's egalitarian praxis.³⁷ James Ingram, in turn, challenges the prevailing assumption that Populism is inherently opposed to cosmopolitanism, suggesting the possibility of a cosmopolitan Populism that transcends nationalist frameworks.³⁸ There are a myriad of arguments explaining the Populist phenomenon as the *opposition*, outweighing the theories of Populism in the position of incumbent government. The next section will further contribute to this debate by applying Hegelian dialectical prism to the Populist's engagement with the constitution.

³¹ Ibid. 60

³² Ibid. 62

³³ Ibid. 63-67

³⁴ Müller, "Populism and Constitutionalism" (2019)

³⁵ Cristóbal Rovira Kaltwasser et al., "Populism: An Overview of the Concept and the State of the Art," essay, in *The Oxford Handbook of Populism* (2019), 15-45.

³⁶ Ibid.

³⁷ Ibid.

³⁸ Ibid.

Constitutional Sublation

Populists may draft and enact constitutions, yet such documents invariably betray the fundamental tenets of constitutional democracy. Rather than institutionalisation of pluralism and safeguarding democracy-constitutive rights—such as freedom of speech and assembly—Populist constitutionalism seeks to negate contestation and to attempt a sublation of a hegemonic vision of the people. Müller argues that populists seek to reshape institutions to serve their interests, maintaining a commitment to governance only as long as institutions produce morally "correct" outcomes.³⁹

Both constitutional negation and constitutional sublation operate within the dialectic of legal and political transformation, but they function in fundamentally different ways. Negation destroys or dismantles an existing constitutional order, while sublation transforms and preserves elements of the old order into a new, supposedly higher form. Constitutional negation occurs when a new political force explicitly rejects and dismantles existing constitutional principles, often under the pretense of restoring a more "authentic" or "democratic" order.⁴⁰ This is a characteristic of Populist constitutionalism, where institutions, legal norms, and rights that constrain majoritarian power are systematically eroded. Sublation is the more sophisticated of the two, in how it does not simply destroy, but instead, incorporates and transforms elements of the old constitutional order into a new synthesis. A constitutional referendum emerging from a dialectics in deliberative democracy or pluralist agonism can be interpreted as sublation by the means of *higher synthesis*.

From Müller's approach, one concludes that the Populists' negation of the constitution is limited to its positionality as the opposition. When in power, they undertake sublation through three key mechanisms identified by Müller: "A kind of colonisation of the state, mass clientelism as well as what political scientists sometimes call discriminatory legalism."⁴¹

In the first mechanism, populists seek to occupy and reconfigure state institutions, eroding judicial independence, dismantling oversight mechanisms, and replacing neutral bureaucracies with partisan loyalists. When full institutional control is not feasible, judicial paralysis—as seen in Poland—becomes the next best option.⁴² Mass clientelism is the exchange of material and immaterial favors for political loyalty. While the exchange of material and symbolic benefits for political loyalty is not unique to Populism, what distinguishes the Populist is its capacity to justify

³⁹ Müller, *What Is Populism?* (2017). 36

⁴⁰ *Ibid.* 35

⁴¹ *Ibid.* 44

⁴² *Ibid.*

such practices as morally legitimate.⁴³ The Populist openly justifies such practices, arguing that only some people—the "real" people—deserve state resources. Lastly, populists selectively enforce laws to punish opponents while shielding their own from accountability.⁴⁴ Civil society organisations that challenge their authority are delegitimised, and labeled as foreign agents or tools of corrupt elites. Through discrediting civil opposition, the Populist reinforces its claim to the exclusive moral representation of the public. Unlike authoritarian regimes that clandestinely undermine opposition, the populist openly recognise this by framing it as a necessary defense of democracy against its enemies.

The sublation is, ergo, completed, as the governance mechanism changes when the Populist engages in the very elite domination they claim to oppose with impunity, transforming the constitution of the liberal democracy—through authoritarian legalism—to an illiberal elective polity.

In an antithesis to this position, I extend an argument through a Hegelian approach to posit that the Populist Constitutionalism fails to achieve true sublation because it cannot resolve its own contradictions. When in opposition, the Populist positions itself as the negation of the constitutional order, framing existing institutions as instruments of elite domination that must be overturned. This antagonism fuels its legitimacy but also locks it into a dependent unilateral relationship with the very system it seeks to overcome. Additionally, Populism cannot reconcile its majoritarian impulse with the pluralist constraints of constitutional democracy; it either—as observed in Müller's work—hollows out of the constitution's substantive principles while preserving its formal husk, or, it provokes crises to justify extrajudicial measures through invoking the *ausnahmezustand*. A constitution that cannot be subverted is then suspended.

The latter path, constituting crises, is another elemental characteristic of the Populist polity. Populists frame political conflicts in apocalyptic terms, presenting themselves as the only legitimate representatives of the people.⁴⁵ Political opposition is not seen as legitimate dissent but as treason. This ongoing *state of siege* helps populists consolidate power while maintaining a position as the sovereign-servant. The Populist systematically frames political conflict in existential terms, presenting itself as the last line of defense against—if not the corrupt elite—an encroaching external threat.⁴⁶ The constitution of crises is observed to be performative. That is, the Populist doesn't resolve the crises; they manufacture and sustain them as a means of legitimising their rule.⁴⁷ Politics is thus reimaged as a permanent state of siege, in which the

⁴³ Ibid.

⁴⁴ Ibid. 45

⁴⁵ Ibid. 68

⁴⁶ Roger Eatwell et al., "Populism and Fascism," essay, in *The Oxford Handbook of Populism* (2019), 461–88.

⁴⁷ Ibid.

Populist alone is the embodiment of the will of the people, a roster of internal and external enemies.

In a clear dialectical approach, sublation is the higher order of synthesis between dialectical opposites that emerges in the resolution of contradiction. In our case, the constitutional order is the thesis built upon pluralism, institutional checks, and procedural democracy. Applying Lefort's notion of democracy as *an empty space*, the thesis exists as a framework that acknowledges *contestation and political uncertainty*. The Populist's antithesis, performed through negation, rejects both pluralism and uncertainty as elite mechanisms. The will of the pure people – embodied in the Populist's actions– is dictated to be a moral alternative to the fallible institutions of liberal democracy.⁴⁸ What emerges from this dialectical antagonism, when the Populist takes charge, is a higher but distorted order that is reconfigured as instruments of exclusion.⁴⁹

In Hegelian terms, this is the negation of the negation – where the Populist's negation holds the seed of its own self-contradiction and self-destruction. One of the flanks of the Populist's political survival after taking on the role of master is perpetuation of crises, which momentarily stabilises the Populist's controlled chaos. Applying the negation of negation, when the old establishment is ousted, the Populist must eventually turn against itself. Internal purges, factionalism, or implosion are common among many populist polities, as seen in cases of the Marxist-Islamist divide in Iran following the 1979 revolution, Peronism in Argentina, or Chávez-Maduro transitions in Venezuela.

⁴⁸ Stefan Rummens et al., "Populism as a Threat to Liberal Democracy," essay, in *The Oxford Handbook of Populism* (2019), 696–718.

⁴⁹ *Ibid.*

Populistic Pseudosublation

I propose the term *pseudosublation* to better describe the spectrality between sublation through *synthesis* and attempt–sublation through *negation of negation*. In the pseudosublation of the constitution, the crisis shifts from the state of exception to a permanent state of siege, where the "exception" becomes permanent, as populist cannot fully resolve the crisis without negating their own claim to power. In this approach, crisis is sublated into a continuous necessity, where it preserves elements of constitutionalism and electorality while simultaneously rejecting the constitutional democracy.

To further refine this argument, I use pseudosublation as a reference to the paradoxical attempt of the Populist to simultaneously sublimate and negate itself as the new Master. The Populist negates its mastery precisely because their authority is contingent on denying that they are the masters or wield power. This is where the Hegelian dialectic takes on a particularly insidious form: the negation of the old master does not lead to a recognition of a new master but rather to an illusory persistence of servitude as *resistance*, even as the Populist rules.

Populist constitutionalism operates as a paradox — it is the power it is resisting. The insistence to remain the authentic voice of the people in the absence of a free and fair electoral process is consolidated through perpetually embattled resistance against an invisible or ever-shifting elite.

There are, however, cases where the *populistic actors* successfully sublimate a new governance through the reinforced democratic mechanisms of the constitution. Roosevelt's (1933-1945) presidency represents one of the stronger cases where the spectrality of a Populist reaches sublation. Before Roosevelt, the American economic and political system was dominated by technate elites, weak social protection, and laissez-faire policies. The Great Depression revealed—in its true Greek sense of Apokalypsis—the contradictions of unregulated capitalism. This created the space for Roosevelt to mobilise the working-class *–the true people–* grievances while attacking the Wall Street *elites* blamed for the Great Depression. This negation of the elite masters, after his election, followed the New Deal to synthesise as the sublation of Roosevelt's movement. The New Deal didn't end capitalism nor Wall Street; it reconfigured the private sector while introducing social safety nets and regulations. What diverges Roosevelt's Populism from the convention of Müller's theses, is Roosevelt's institutionalisation of policies to resolve the crises he crusaded against, instead of perpetuating them. However, since Roosevelt's populist conduct does not fully fit within the framework of Populism defined by Müller, we can argue sublation remains exclusive to constitutionalists – not populists.

For cases which fit the seven theses of populism, to consolidate their power, the Populist must subvert the dialectic through the negation of negations – the denial of their own mastery. The Populist displaces the dialectical antagonism onto an abstraction: a deep state, a foreign enemy, an internal traitor—forces that keep the resistance alive and obscure the reality of their own domination.

What we have identified as *pseudosublation* is a failed sublation. Contradictions are not overcome. They're suspended in artificial permanence through cycles of crises and mobilisation that prevent resolution. The Populist remains, in its narrative, a *servant of the people*, even as they control the institutions of the state, dismantle checks and balances, and reshape the constitutional order in their image. Revolutionary Populist and Populist Authoritarian polities such as those in Russia, Venezuela, Cuba, and Iran are uniquely resilient as they thrive on their own self-conception as perpetually embattled rather than institutionally entrenched polities.

Pseudosublation also holds as a theory to be incorporated into future empirical studies of Populism, considering the cases of liberal erosion in Constitutional Democracies. Populist governance, as exemplified by Orbán, Trump, and Erdoğan, also operates through pseudosublation. In all three cases, populists refuse the finality of mastery, negating their own dominance by constructing an ever-shifting elite enemy—Brussels, globalists, deep-state actors—ensuring that political power remains structurally contingent on the continuous reproduction of crisis rather than its resolution.

Rooduijn's critique of the Populist Zeitgeist offers a final perspective on pseudosublation as a recurring but incomplete force. He rejects the notion that Populism constitutes a structurally dominant force, and instead presents it as a periodic political mood, emerging in response to moments of systemic failure before dissipating once its contradictions render it untenable. This complements our epilogue, as the failure of Populists to achieve true sublation. Returning to the spectre – as a political apparition per the conventional use of it— Rooduijn concludes that Populism returns in spectral form, haunting the very structures it fails to overturn. Rooduijn's work also arrives at a conclusion similar to pseudosublation to describe the political behaviour of the Populist: It fails to culminate in the triumph of the true people over the master who is always just beyond reach.

Conclusion

Populism's engagement with the political order is defined by constant antagonism, never reaching resolution. In opposition, it assumes the role of the Servant, demanding recognition from the ruling elite while portraying the constitutional framework as fundamentally illegitimate. But unlike Hegel's Servant, who ultimately transforms and achieves self-conscious mastery through struggle, the Populist does not transcend this role once in power. Instead of integrating into the system, the Populist remains locked in a logic of negation, perpetuating crisis as a means of political survival. The failure to achieve sublation lies in the contradiction of Populism's claim to represent the absolute will of the people.

Upon capturing power, the Populist does not resolve these contradictions; rather, it generates new crises—targeting the judiciary, the press, bureaucratic institutions, and international actors—to ensure that governance remains an extension of opposition rather than a resolution of it. This work has termed this phenomenon pseudosublation. Unlike movements that successfully institutionalise their reforms, populists fail to transition from negation to governance; they consolidate power while maintaining the rhetoric of resistance, and sustaining their legitimacy through the mechanisation of crisis.

Through the Master-Servant dialectic, Hegel provides a lens to examine how Populism neither negates the old order completely nor creates a sustainable alternative. By applying Hegelian dialectics to Populism, we see Populism as a liminal Spectre between negation and sublation, mastery and servitude, sovereignty and resistance – a rejection of the binary of Master and Servant and never fully being either. It neither integrates into constitutionalism nor fully overcomes it. The spectrality of its political order remains defined by crises of consolidation.

What Pseudosublation offers to future empirical studies of populism, is a dialectical framework for understanding why populists –upon seizing power– fail to resolve the contradictions that propelled them to dominance. It explains how populism negates the existing order without producing a true synthesis, ensuring that governance is structured around the deferral of resolution rather than the consolidation. Pseudosublation provides a methodological lens to analyse how populists engage in a self-negating dialectic, and enables scholars to trace the movement of contradiction in populist governance, distinguishing between cases where populists transition into stable autocracy, remain in suspended antagonism, or collapse under their own unsustainable negations.

Bibliography

1. Albertazzi, Daniele, and Duncan McDonnell. *Twenty-first century populism: The spectre of Western European democracy*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 2008.
2. Aristotelis Fusiek, David. "Hegel in a Postcolonial World: Populist Authoritarianism, Postcolonialism, and the Master–Slave Dialectic." *Central European Journal of Politics* 7, no. 2 (2022): 4–30. https://doi.org/10.24132/cejop_2021_6.
3. Eatwell, Roger, Paul A. Taggart, Paulina Ochoa Espejo, and Pierre Ostiguy. "Populism and Fascism." Essay. In *The Oxford Handbook of Populism*, 461–88. Oxford, United Kingdom: Oxford University Press, 2019.
4. Hawkins, Kirk A., Paul A. Taggart, Paulina Ochoa Espejo, and Pierre Ostiguy. "Populism and Its Causes." Essay. In *The Oxford Handbook of Populism*, 340–65. Oxford, United Kingdom: Oxford University Press, 2019.
5. Hegel, Georg Wilhelm Friedrich, A. V. Miller, and J. N. Findlay. *Phenomenology of spirit by G.W.F. Hegel. Transl. by A.V. Miller with analysis of the text and foreword by J.N. Findlay*. Oxford: Oxford Univ. Press, 1977.
6. Ionescu, Ghița., and Ernest Gellner. *Populism; its meaning and national characteristics. edited by Ghița Ionescu and Ernest Gellner*. New York: Macmillan, 1969.
7. Kelly, Dunkan, Paul A. Taggart, Paulina Ochoa Espejo, and Pierre Ostiguy. "Populism and the History of Popular Sovereignty." Essay. In *The Oxford Handbook of Populism*, 642–72. Oxford, United Kingdom: Oxford University Press, 2019.
8. Kochi, Tarik. "The End of Global Constitutionalism and Rise of Antidemocratic Politics." *Global Society* 34, no. 4 (April 16, 2020): 487–506. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13600826.2020.1749037>.
9. Mudde, Cas. "Populism: An Ideational Approach." Essay. In *The Oxford Handbook of Populism*, 2019th ed., 45–71. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2019.
10. Mudde, Cas. "The Populist Zeitgeist." *Government and Opposition* 39, no. 4 (2004): 541–63. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1477-7053.2004.00135.x>.
11. Müller, Jan-Werner. *What is populism?* London: Penguin Books, 2017.
12. Müller, Jan-Werner, Paul A. Taggart, Paulina Ochoa Espejo, and Pierre Ostiguy. "Populism and Constitutionalism." Essay. In *The Oxford Handbook of Populism*, 743–65. Oxford, United Kingdom: Oxford University Press, 2019.
13. Rooduijn, Matthijs. "A Populist Zeitgeist? The Impact of Populism on Parties, Media and the Public in Western Europe." *Thesis, fully internal, Universiteit van Amsterdam*, 2013. <https://doi.org/https://dare.uva.nl>.
14. Rovira Kaltwasser, Cristóbal, Paul A. Taggart, Paulina Ochoa Espejo, and Pierre Ostiguy. "Populism: An Overview of the Concept and the State of the Art." Essay. In *The Oxford Handbook of Populism*, 15–45. Oxford, United Kingdom: Oxford University Press, 2019.

15. Rovira Kaltwasser, Cristóbal, Paul A. Taggart, Paulina Ochoa Espejo, and Pierre Ostiguy. *The Oxford Handbook of Populism*. Oxford, United Kingdom: Oxford University Press, 2019.
16. Rummens, Stefan, Paul A. Taggart, Paulina Ochoa Espejo, and Pierre Ostiguy. “Populism as a Threat to Liberal Democracy.” Essay. In *The Oxford Handbook of Populism*, 696–718. Oxford, United Kingdom: Oxford University Press, 2019.
17. Sinnerbrink, Robert. “Recognitive Freedom: Hegel and the Problem of Recognition.” *Contemporary Perspectives in Critical and Social Philosophy*, January 1, 2004, 271–95. https://doi.org/10.1163/9789047406648_010.
18. Weyland, Kurt, Paul A. Taggart, Paulina Ochoa Espejo, and Pierre Ostiguy. “Populism: A Political-Strategic Approach.” Essay. In *The Oxford Handbook of Populism*, 71–103. Oxford, United Kingdom: Oxford University Press, 2019.

Declaration of originality

I hereby declare that I have written this seminar paper on my own, have not used any sources or aids other than those specified, and have marked the passages taken from them as such. All aids used are listed in the table below. Regarding the use of Large Language Models (LLM, e.g. Chat-GPT), I have archived the entire LLM interaction history with reference to the submitted work and can present it upon request. This seminar paper has not been presented in this or a similar form in any other course.

Name of aid	Purpose
Perplexity	Alternative to Google; literature research
Grammarly Plugin*	First proofreader, syntax and dictation corrections
ChatGPT	Second proofreader, fine-tuning the syntax and dictation, corrections, assistance in wording/articulating the Research Question and Title